

Intent-Adaptive Haptic Rendering Based on Selective Attention

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Abstract. This study investigates intent-adaptive haptic rendering, where haptic feedback is selectively presented based on user intent in multi-object environments. We examine distractor attenuation (Full, Reduced, Single) and off-screen continuity (ACT vs. INACT) using a multi-object tracking task with positional identification (Pos) and bounce count (Count). Results show no significant differences when visual information is continuously available. Under reduced visibility, a significant main effect of haptic condition was observed for Pos, while no significant effects were found for continuity or Count. Mean trends indicate lower performance in Full and higher performance in Reduced and Single. These findings suggest that non-selective haptic presentation may introduce interference, and that adaptive modulation of haptic feedback shows potential benefits, although further validation is required.

Keywords: Haptic Rendering, Selective Attention, Multi-object Interaction, Personalization, FEEL TECH

1 Introduction

Advances in multisensory systems have enabled the integration of haptic feedback with visual and auditory information. Visual attention is inherently selective and guided by user intent, often focusing on a target among multiple elements. However, how such intent-driven selectivity should be reflected in haptic presentation remains unresolved. In particular, it is unclear whether haptic feedback should be uniformly presented for all visually available objects or selectively provided only for the attended target. When visual information is absent (e.g., off-screen), it is unclear whether haptic feedback should be suppressed or maintained to support target tracking. This study investigates haptic rendering in multi-object environments from an intent-adaptive perspective grounded in FEEL TECH [1], which emphasizes personalized adaptation of sensory information for the receiver.

2 Related Work

Conventional haptics research has focused on multisensory synchronization, often modeled by Maximum Likelihood Estimation [2]. Prior studies have reported that responses to haptic stimuli are subject to temporal and spatial masking [3], suggesting potential perceptual interference when multiple stimuli are presented. In addition, prior work on digital touch communication suggests that haptic interaction can support perception when visual information is limited [4]. Whether similar benefits extend to

multi-object environments remains an open question, particularly in dynamic tracking scenarios. In this study, we examine how selective attenuation and haptic continuity affect perception in target tracking tasks.

3 Haptic Rendering and Experimental Setup

3.1 Intent-Adaptive Rendering

Haptic feedback was modulated based on user focus by controlling the relative intensity of target (H_{target}) and distractor signals (H_{others}). Three on-screen mixing conditions were tested: Full (all signals presented), Reduced (distractors attenuated by -9 dB), and Single (only target presented). In addition, off-screen continuity was manipulated: ACT (haptics sustained off-screen) and INACT (haptics terminated when the target left the visible area).

3.2 Apparatus and Procedure

Visual stimuli were presented on a 27-inch display (60 fps). Participants held a handheld device equipped with a voice-coil actuator, through which haptic feedback was presented without any accompanying auditory stimuli. The task involved tracking one target among six moving objects and reporting its final position (Pos) and bounce count (Count). Haptic feedback consisted of continuous pink noise representing rolling motion and decaying sine waves representing boundary impacts.

3.3 Experimental Design

Ten participants completed two experiments with trials including a 30-second motion period, with conditions presented in random order within each experiment.

Exp. 1 (On-Screen): All objects remained visible (4 trajectories \times 3 conditions).

Exp. 2 (Off-Screen): Objects could move outside the visible area (3 trajectories \times 2 continuity conditions \times 3 mixing conditions). Approximately 25% of the virtual space was outside the visible area, with the display showing a 1024×1024 px region within a larger 1182×1182 px field, with the off-screen area in the bottom-right.

Fig. 1. Examples of visual stimuli: (a) Initial frame (the target is indicated by an arrow showing its moving direction); (b) Intermediate frame; (c) Response screen.

4 Results and Discussion

For positional accuracy (Pos) in Exp. 1 (On-Screen), no statistically significant differences were observed across conditions (Full: 0.65, Reduced: 0.725, Single: 0.725; Friedman, $p = 0.55$). For count accuracy (Count), Reduced showed a higher mean (0.675) than Full (0.525) and Single (0.65), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.17$). Despite the lack of significance, Full consistently yielded lower performance, suggesting that presenting all haptic signals may introduce interference when visual information is sufficient.

In Exp. 2 (Off-Screen), positional accuracy (Pos) showed a significant main effect of

Fig. 2. Exp. 1 (on-screen): Pos and Count across haptic conditions.

Fig. 3. Exp. 2 (off-screen): Pos and Count across ACT/INACT and distractor conditions.

haptic condition ($F(2,18) = 4.16, p = 0.03$). Although neither continuity (ACT/INACT) nor the interaction reached significance, follow-up analyses revealed that under the INACT condition, the Full condition yielded significantly lower performance than both the Reduced ($p=0.02$) and Single ($p=0.03$). For Count, no significant main effects were observed; however, ACT tended to produce slightly higher values than INACT with substantial variability. Follow-up analyses further showed that this tendency reached significance in the Full condition, where ACT outperformed INACT ($p=0.02$).

These results suggest that haptic feedback should not be uniformly presented across all objects. The consistent degradation in the Full condition suggests that suppressing non-target signals is beneficial, even under reduced visibility. While statistical evidence for context-dependent modulation (e.g., ACT vs. INACT) remains limited, the observed tendencies align with an intent-adaptive approach in which haptic information is selectively optimized rather than exhaustively presented and may also indicate a potential benefit of maintaining haptic feedback even when the target moves off-screen.

5 Open Research Questions and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Design principles for haptic feedback in multi-object settings remain open questions, particularly in selecting and configuring relevant factors under selective attention. We invite discussion from cognitive science and signal processing to clarify issues including and extending beyond those examined here.

References

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